

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Change of Mg and K concentrations for 40 years in the Düzce atmosphere by *Pinus pinaster* annual rings

Elnaji Abdulaziz Ahmida SALEH¹ and Hatice COBANOĞLU^{2,*}

¹ Department of Geography College of Education, Al-Qubba Branch, University of Derna, Libya.

² Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Faculty of Forestry, Department of Forest Engineering, Düzce University, Düzce, Türkiye.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(03), 560–567

Publication history: Received on 08 November 2022; revised on 16 December 2022; accepted on 18 December 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.3.1372>

Abstract

Air is one of the most essential elements that living things need to survive. Air pollution has become even more important due to reasons such as population growth and the difficulties brought by global warming and war. The factors that make up air pollution are also one of the most important factors of environmental pollution and cause serious pollution problems. While some metals in the air positively affect plant growth as nutrient elements in agricultural activities, they cause deterioration of plant development due to the accumulation of high concentrations in plant organs. This study, as an indicator of the time-dependent variation of Mg and K concentrations with atmospheric accumulation, reveals the variation and year-related amounts of *Pinus pinaster* species in Düzce province.

Keywords: Accumulation; Environmental; Trace metal; Indicator; Nutrient; Wood

1. Introduction

Very few of the lands on earth are suitable for agriculture, and the lands cultivated in limited areas are under pollution pressure for various reasons today [1-9]. On existing agricultural lands; Developing industrial activities, fertilizers and pesticides used in agricultural production, exhaust gases and zoning problems have caused pollution problems in agricultural lands [10-17]. In order to benefit from annual ring effectively, it is necessary to know the sources of metals, which are indicators of air pollution, and then to find a solution for them [18-27].

Population growth, which gained momentum with urbanization, also caused various environmental problems [28-36]. Industrial activities developed in our country due to technological developments have triggered migration from villages to cities and cause unplanned population growth [37-40]. High population growth rate, industrial facilities, exhaust gases from vehicles and mineral fuels cause air pollution [41-46]. Industrial plants, mineral fuels and vehicle exhaust emissions are the most important air pollutants in our country and worldwide, and they significantly threaten human health [47-55]. Today, many factors cause environmental pollution [56-64]. These; Agricultural fertilizers and pesticides used for agricultural purposes, industrialization, and human-induced, heavy metal-sourced waste [64-68]. When these factors are evaluated, atmospheric heavy metals are emphasized as the most critical air pollutant [69-73]. It is very important to evaluate trees in terms of heavy metal pollution, which is one of the most critical threats to human and environmental health [74-78].

This study aimed to determine the time-dependent change of K and Mg concentration of *Pinus pinaster* located in Düzce, which is among the cities with the most polluted air among European cities, on a regional basis.

* Corresponding author: Hatice COBANOĞLU

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample preparation

The study will be carried out on a *Pinus pinaster* tree grown in Düzce. The ring samples to be used within the scope of the study were obtained during the cutting made in Düzce City Cemetery in February 2022, by marking the north direction on the log and taking its coordinates. The log provided was examined and determined to be 40 years old. If the experiment is approved, the upper surface of the log will be smoothed by sanding so that the annual rings can be seen more clearly in the laboratory. Within the scope of the study, considering the annual ring widths, they will be grouped between 1 and 8 from the outside to the inside, each 5 years. After the wood surface is divided into groups and the age ranges are determined, samples will be taken from wood in every age range with the help of a steel-tipped drill and placed in glass petri dishes. The wood samples to be taken will be shredded and turned into sawdust. During these processes, care will be taken not to use tools made of metals that are the subject of the study.

2.2. Sample analyses

Samples will be sieved after they are room-dried and placed in glass petri dishes. The samples taken in glass containers will be kept in the laboratory with their mouths open until they become room-dry, and the samples that have become room-dry will be dried in an oven at 45 °C for two weeks. 0.5 g of the samples to be dried will be taken and 6 ml of 65% HNO₃ and 2 ml of 35% H₂O₂ will be added and placed in the microwave oven. The program of the microwave device will be adjusted to go up to 200 °C in 15 minutes and stay at 200 °C for 15 minutes. After the samples are burned in the microwave oven, the samples that have become solution will be taken into scaled balloon test tubes and made up to 50 ml with ultrapure water, metal analyzes will be made with the ICP-OES device. The analysis results will be multiplied by 100 as the samples are taken 0.5 gr and made up to 50 gr with water. According to the analysis results that do not fall into the calibration graph, different calibration graphs will be created at the ppm level and re-reading will be done. The main expense item in the research is service procurement for heavy metal analyzes to be made with the help of the ICP-OES device. Heavy metal analyzes will be performed in an accredited central research laboratory. All measurements within the scope of the paper will be made in 3 repetitions. Variance analysis will be applied to the obtained data using SPSS 21.0 package program, Duncan test will be applied for the factors determined as a result of variance analysis that there is statistically significant difference between them at least 95% confidence level (p<0.05). The data to be obtained will be interpreted by tabulating, and thus it will be tried to determine how the concentrations of the elements in the study have changed from past to present.

3. Results and discussion

The change of Mg (ppm) concentrations in annual rings by periods and directions and the statistical analysis results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Change of Mg (ppm) Concentration by periods and direction in annual rings

Years	North	East	South	West	F Value	Average
2017-2021	308.8 Ce	358.9 De	234.0 Be	162.4 Af	1082.7***	266.0 bc
2012-2016	260.2 Dd	161.9 Bb	189.7 Cc	113.0 Ab	1856.9***	181.2 ab
2007-2011	221.7 Bb	223.7 Bc	150.6 Aa	147.8 Ae	404.3***	186.0 ab
2002-2006	238.6 Cc	287.9 Dd	207.3 Bd	150.0 Ae	1098.4***	221.0 ab
1997-2001	568.0 Dg	459.0 Cg	204.7 Bd	138.0 Ad	15788.6***	342.4 c
1992-1996	45,2 Cf	521.5 Dh	317.2 Bg	113.3 Ab	11145.9***	351.0 c
1987-1991	30,9 De	47.0 Aa	156.7 Cb	108.4 Ba	6334.3***	154.8 a
1982-1986	149.5 Ba	382.7 Df	279.8 Cf	129.2 Ac	1527.7***	235.3 ab
F Value	2839.4***	3781.6***	1261.3***	434.7***		5.3***
Average	313.2 C	305.3 C	217.5 B	132.8 A	16.185***	

According to Duncan's test results, the letters a, b, etc., represent the statistical differences between organs. ns: not significant. *** significant at 0.001 level.

When the change of Mg concentration was examined, it was determined that the change was statistically significant (at least $p < 0.05$) on the basis of period in all directions and based on direction in all periods. According to the average values, the lowest Mg concentration was obtained in 1987-1991, while the highest Mg concentrations were obtained in 1992-2001. On the directional basis, the lowest concentrations were obtained in the west and the highest in north and east directions. The Mg concentration changes by organ, and direction and the statistical analysis results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Changes in Mg (ppm) concentrations by direction and organs

Organ	North	East	South	West	F Value	Average
Outer Bark	1764.7 Db	460.8 B	662.8 Cb	313.8 Ab	29817.0***	800.5 b
Inner Bark	203.6 Aa	346.8 C	217.5 Ba	355.1 Dc	4956.4***	280.8 a
Wood	313.2 Ca	305.3 C	217.5 Ba	132.8 Aa	16.1***	242.2 a
F Value	204.5***	1.7 ns	103.3***	313.2***		35.6***
Average	447.4 C	325.0 BC	262.0 AB	173.1 A	6.089**	

According to Duncan's test results, the letters a, b, etc., represent the statistical differences between organs. ns: not significant. ** significant at 0.01level, *** significant at 0.001 level.

When the change of Mg concentration on the basis of organ was examined, it was determined that the change on the basis of organ in all directions except the east direction and on the direction basis in all organs was statistically significant (at least $p < 0.05$). According to the average values, the lowest Mg concentrations were obtained in the inner bark and wood, while the highest Mg concentration was obtained in the outer bark. Based on direction, a change is observed in the form of west<south<east<north. The change of K (ppm) concentrations in annual rings by periods and directions and the statistical analysis results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Change of K (ppm) concentration by periods and direction in annual rings

Years	North	East	South	West	F Value	Average
2017-2021	446.3 Bg	47.1 Aa	535.9 Cg	631.4 Dg	5408.8***	415.2 b
2012-2016	64.3 Aa	78.9 Ab	460.7 Be	715.5 Ch	4114.6***	329.8 b
2007-2011	58.3 Aa	149.8 Bc	389.2 Cc	611.0 Df	1879.6***	302.0 ab
2002-2006	348.0 Bf	165.2 Ad	430.0 Cd	575.6 De	1233.4***	379.7 b
1997-2001	332.0 Be	53.9 Aa	326.9 Bb	440.2 Cd	4410.0***	288.2 ab
1992-1996	258.7 Cd	58.6 Aa	497.9 Df	237.6 Bc	3028.3***	263.2 ab
1987-1991	137.0 c	UL	UL	137.6 a	0,0 ns	137.3 a
1982-1986	103.0 b	UL	131.4 a	166.9 b	144.7***	133.8 a
F Value	2227.5***	112.1***	1774.1***	1945.3***		2.6*
Average	218.4 B	92.2 A	396.0 C	439.5 C	22.838***	

According to Duncan's test results, the letters a, b, etc., represent the statistical differences between organs. ns: not significant. * significant at 0.05level, *** significant at 0.001 level.

When the change of K concentration on the basis of age was examined, it was determined that the change on the basis of age in all directions and on the basis of direction in all ages was statistically significant (at least $p < 0.05$). According to the average values, the lowest K concentrations were obtained in the period of 1982-1986, while the highest K concentration was obtained in 2012-2021. Based on direction, the lowest K concentration was obtained in the east, and the highest Mg concentrations were obtained in the south and west directions. The K concentration changes by organ, and direction and the statistical analysis results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Changes in K (ppm) concentrations by direction and organs

Organ	North	East	South	West	F Value	Average
Outer Bark	675.7 Cb	126.2 Ab	292.4 Bb	1218.5 Db	7604.4***	578.2 b
Inner Bark	104.9 Ba	46.3 Aa	89.7 Ba	651.6 Ca	2433.9***	223.1 a
Wood	218.4 Ba	92.2 Aab	396.0 Cb	439.5 Ca	22.8***	296.2 a
F Value	18.5***	2.4 ns	9.3**	20.3***		8.1**
Average	252.8 B	90.7 A	350.4 B	538.6 C	22.663***	

According to Duncan's test results, the letters a, b, etc., represent the statistical differences between organs. ns: not significant. ** significant at 0,01 level, *** Significant at 0.001 level.

When the change of K concentration based on organs was examined, it was determined that the change on the basis of organ in all directions except the east direction and on the basis of direction in all organs was statistically significant (at least $p < 0.05$). According to the average values, the lowest K concentrations were obtained in the inner bark and wood, while the highest K concentration was obtained in the outer bark. On the basis of direction, the lowest value was obtained in the east and the highest value in the west direction, while the north and south directions were in the same group as a result of the Duncan test.

Trace metals have been the subject of many studies in recent years, as they are elements that can be extremely harmful to human and environmental health in high concentrations [79-81]. The study determined the densities of different metals in various tree species depending on air pollution [82-84]. As a result of the evaluation of the analysis results, it has been determined that all heavy metals are in different types and amounts, and it is thought that these amounts are due to the high vehicular traffic of the region in the sampling area [84-86]. When the variation of K and Mg concentrations is examined, it is seen that the changes differ in a statistically significant level. Study has been done. It is aimed to determine the heavy metal pollution concentrations in landscape plants obtained in different cities [87-90].

4. Conclusion

As a result of the research, it was observed that the Zn, Pb, Mn and Ni elements in the samples taken from the points close to the highways were in higher concentrations than the samples taken from the places far from the highways. Although many species are used in biomonitor studies, the accumulation levels of species are still being investigated in terms of their usability as biomonitors. However, suitable climate type and soil structure support this. As a result, annual rings of *Pinus pinaster* tree may also be suitable for other metals and pollutants, as evidence of its usability in measuring air quality.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they no conflict of interest. The none of the authors have any competing interests in the manuscript.

References

- [1] Kilicoglu C, Cetin M, Aricak B, Sevik H. Site selection by using the multi-criteria technique-a case study of Bafra, Turkey. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2020; 192(9), 1-12.
- [2] Isinkaralar O, & Varol C. A cellular automata-based approach for spatio-temporal modeling of the city center as a complex system: The case of Kastamonu, Türkiye. *Cities*. 2023; 132, 104073.
- [3] Kilicoglu C, Cetin M, Aricak B, Sevik H. Integrating multicriteria decision-making analysis for a GIS-based settlement area in the district of Atakum, Samsun, Turkey. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*. 2021; 143, 379–388.
- [4] Isinkaralar O, Varol C, & Yilmaz D. Digital mapping and predicting the urban growth: Integrating scenarios into cellular automata—Markov chain modeling. *Applied Geomatics*. 2022; 14(4), 695–705.

- [5] Cetin M, Sevik H, & Isinkaralar K. Changes in the particulate matter and CO₂ concentrations based on the time and weather conditions: the case of Kastamonu. *Oxidation Communications*. 2017; 40(1-II), 477-485.
- [6] Gencil O, Nodehi M, Bayraktar OY, Kaplan G, Benli A, Gholampour A, & Ozbakkaloglu T. Basalt fiber-reinforced foam concrete containing silica fume: An experimental study. *Construction and Building Materials*. 2022; 326, 126861.
- [7] Işınkaralar K, Işınkaralar Ö, & Şevik H. Usability of Some Landscape Plants in Biomonitoring Technique: an Anaysis with Special Regard to Heavy Metals. *Kent Akademisi*. 2022; 15(3), 1413-1421.
- [8] Cetin M, Aljama AMO, Alrabiti OBM, Adiguzel F, Sevik H, & Zeren Cetin I. Determination and Mapping of Regional Change of Pb and Cr Pollution in Ankara City Center. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*. 2022; 233(5), 1-10.
- [9] Ucun Ozel H, Gemici BT, Gemici E, Ozel HB, Cetin M, Sevik H. Application of artificial neural networks to predict the heavy metal contamination in the Bartın River. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2020; 1-18.
- [10] Sütçüoğlu GG, & Önaç AK. A site selection model proposal for sustainable urban regeneration: case study of Karşıyaka, İzmir, Turkey. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2022; 194(5), 1-23.
- [11] Kalaycı Önaç A, & Gönüllü Sütçüoğlu G. Effect of urban change on place attachment: evidence from two locations from a city in Turkey with similar historical landscape values. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*. 2021; 14(11), 1-17.
- [12] Önaç AK, & Altunsoy H. Cultural and spatial changes caused by intensive migration in urban areas; evidence from Hatay, Turkey. *Turkish Journal of Forest Science*. 2020; 4(2), 270-281.
- [13] Işınkaralar K. Kütahya kent merkezinde hava kalitesinin zamansal ve mekansal değişimi. *Mühendislik Bilimleri ve Tasarım Dergisi*. 2022; 10(1), 152-160.
- [14] Isinkaralar K. Theoretical removal study of gas form BTEX onto activated carbon produced from *Digitalis purpurea* L. biomass. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-022-02558-2>.
- [15] Isinkaralar K. Performance of gas-phase toluene by adsorption onto activated carbon prepared from *Robinia pseudoacacia* L. as lignocellulosic material. *Sakarya University Journal of Science*. 2022; 26(2), 410-420.
- [16] Cetin M, Onac AK, Sevik H, & Sen B. Temporal and regional change of some air pollution parameters in Bursa. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. 2019; 12(3), 311-316.
- [17] Elsunousi AAM, Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozel HB, Ucun Ozel H. Periodical and regional change of particulate matter and CO₂ concentration in Misurata. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2021; 193, 707(2021).
- [18] Öztürk S, & Işınkaralar Ö. Parking problematique in Kastamonu city center: A critical evaluation. *The Journal of International Social Research*. 2019; 12(67), 506-511.
- [19] Ghoma W, Sevik H, & Isinkaralar K. Using indoor plants as biomonitors for detection of toxic metals by tobacco smoke. *Air, Quality and Atmosphere & Health*. 2022; 15, 415-424.
- [20] Elajail ISI, Sevik H, Ozel HB, & Isik B. Examining the chemical compositions of mineral concrete agents in terms of their environmental effects. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin*. 2022; 31(9), 9784-9790.
- [21] Işınkaralar K. Evaluation of environmental barium concentration biomonitoring in tree rings. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*. 2022; 10(4), 754-759.
- [22] Cesur A, Zeren Cetin I, Cetin M, Sevik H, & Ozel HB. The use of *Cupressus arizonica* as a biomonitor of Li, Fe, and Cr pollution in Kastamonu. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*. 2022; 233(6), 1-9.
- [23] Aricak B, Cetin M, Erdem R, Sevik H, & Cometen H. The change of some heavy metal concentrations in scotch pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) depending on traffic density, organelle and washing. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*. 2019; 17(3), 6723-6734.
- [24] Işınkaralar K. Changes in Cadmium (Cd) concentrations in some plants depending on traffic density. *New Trends and Issues Proceedings on Advances in Pure and Applied Sciences*. 2021; (14), 63-70.
- [25] Isinkaralar K. & Turkyilmaz A. Simultaneous adsorption of selected VOCs in the gas environment by low-cost adsorbent from *Ricinus communis*. *Carbon Letters*. 2022; 32(7), 1781-1789.
- [26] Ucun Ozel H, Ozel HB, Cetin M, Sevik H, Gemici BT, & Varol T. (2019). Base alteration of some heavy metal concentrations on local and seasonal in Bartın River. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2019; 191(9), 594.

- [27] Işınkaralar K. & Erdem R. The effect of atmospheric deposition on potassium accumulation in several tree species as a biomonitor. *Environmental Research and Technology*. 2022; 5(1), 94-100.
- [28] Turkyılmaz A, Sevik H, Isinkaralar K, & Cetin M. Use of tree rings as a bioindicator to observe atmospheric heavy metal deposition. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2019; 26(5), 5122-5130.
- [29] Isinkaralar K, Gullu G, Turkyılmaz A, Dogan M, & Turhan O. Activated carbon production from horse chestnut shells for hydrogen storage. *International Journal of Global Warming*. 2022; 26(4), 361-373.
- [30] Isinkaralar K, Koc I, Erdem R, Sevik H. Atmospheric Cd, Cr, and Zn deposition in several landscape plants in Mersin. *Türkiye, Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*. 2022; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-022-05607-8>.
- [31] Savas DS, Sevik H, Isinkaralar K, Turkyılmaz A, Cetin M. The potential of using *Cedrus atlantica* as a biomonitor in the concentrations of Cr and Mn. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2021; 28(39), 55446-55453.
- [32] Saleh EAA, & Işınkaralar Ö. Analysis of trace elements accumulation in some landscape plants as an indicator of pollution in an urban environment: Case of Ankara. *Kastamonu University Journal of Engineering and Sciences*. 2022; 8(1), 1-5.
- [33] Isinkaralar K, Erdem R. Landscape plants as biomonitors for Magnesium concentration in some species. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*. 2021; 29(2), 468-473.
- [34] Isinkaralar K, Gullu G, & Turkyılmaz A. Experimental study of formaldehyde and BTEX adsorption onto activated carbon from lignocellulosic biomass. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. 2022; 1-11.
- [35] Yılmaz D, & Isinkaralar O. How Can Natural Environment Scoring Tool (Nest) be Adapted for Urban Parks?. *Kastamonu University Journal of Engineering and Sciences*. 2021; 7(2), 127-139.
- [36] Isinkaralar K. Some atmospheric trace metals deposition in selected trees as a possible biomonitor. *Romanian Biotechnological Letters*. 2022; 27(1), 3227-3236.
- [37] Yılmaz D, & Isinkaralar O. Climate action plans under climate-resilient urban policies. *Kastamonu University Journal of Engineering and Sciences*. 2021; 7(2), 140-147.
- [38] Turkyılmaz A, Cetin M, Sevik H, Isinkaralar, & Saleh EAA. Variation of heavy metal accumulation in certain landscaping plants due to traffic density. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. 2020; 22(3), 2385-2398.
- [39] Işınkaralar Ö, & Varol Ç. Kent merkezlerinde ticaret birimlerin mekânsal örüntüsü üzerine bir değerlendirme: Kastamonu örneği. *Journal of Architectural Sciences and Applications*. 2021; 6(2), 396-403.
- [40] Çetin M, Şevik H, Türkyılmaz A, Işınkaralar K. Using Abies's needles as biomonitors of recent heavy metal accumulation. *Kastamonu University Journal of Engineering and Sciences*. 2021; 7(1), 1-6.
- [41] Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozturk A, Ozel HB, Pinar B. Changes in Pb, Cr and Cu concentrations in some bioindicators depending on traffic density on the basis of species and organs. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*. 2019; 17(6), 12843-12857.
- [42] Cetin M, Sevik H, Turkyılmaz A, Isinkaralar K. Using Abies's needles as biomonitors of recent heavy metal accumulation. *Kastamonu University Journal of Engineering and Sciences*. 2021; 7(1), 1-6.
- [43] Isinkaralar K. Atmospheric deposition of Pb and Cd in the *Cedrus atlantica* for environmental biomonitoring. *Landscape Ecological Engineering*. 2022; 1-10.
- [44] Cetin M, Sevik H, & Cobanoğlu O. Ca, Cu, and Li in washed and unwashed specimens of needles, bark, and branches of the blue spruce (*Picea pungens*) in the city of Ankara. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2020; 27(17), 21816-21825.
- [45] Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozel HB, Akarsu H, & Cetin IZ. Analyzing of usability of tree-rings as biomonitors for monitoring heavy metal accumulation in the atmosphere in urban area: a case study of cedar tree (*Cedrus* sp.). *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2020; 192(1), 23.
- [46] Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozel HU, Ozel HB, Mossi MMM, & Cetin IZ. Determination of Pb and Mg accumulation in some of the landscape plants in shrub forms. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2020; 27(2), 2423-2431.
- [47] Karacocuk T, Sevik H, Isinkaralar K, Turkyılmaz A, Cetin M. The change of Cr and Mn concentrations in selected plants in Samsun city center depending on traffic density. *Landscape Ecological Engineering*. 2022; 18, 75-83.
- [48] Chen S, Yao Q, Chen X, Liu J, Chen D, Ou T, ... & Fang K. Tree-ring recorded variations of 10 heavy metal elements over the past 168 years in southeastern China. *Elementa Science Anthropocene*. 2021; 9(1), 00075.

- [49] Cetin M, & Jawed AA. Variation of Ba concentrations in some plants grown in Pakistan depending on traffic density. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*. 2022; 1-7.
- [50] Peana M, Medici S, Dadar M, Zoroddu MA, Pelucelli A, Chasapis CT, & Bjørklund G. Environmental barium: Potential exposure and health-hazards. *Archives of Toxicology*. 2021; 95(8), 2605-2612.
- [51] Ren Y, Luo Q, Zhuo S, Hu Y, Shen G, Cheng, & Tao, S. Bioaccessibility and public health risk of heavy metal (loid) s in the airborne particulate matter of four cities in northern China. *Chemosphere*. 2021; 277, 130312.
- [52] Sevik H, Ozel HB, Cetin M, Özel HU, & Erdem T. Determination of changes in heavy metal accumulation depending on plant species, plant organism, and traffic density in some landscape plants. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. 2019c; 12(2), 189-195.
- [53] Turkyilmaz A, Sevik H, Cetin M, & Ahmaida Saleh EA. Changes in heavy metal accumulation depending on traffic density in some landscape plants. *Polish Journal Environmental Studies*. 2018c; 27(5), 2277–2284.
- [54] Bayraktar EP, Isinkaralar O, & Isinkaralar K. Usability of several species for monitoring and reducing the heavy metal pollution threatening the public health in urban environment of Ankara. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2022; 14(3), 276-283.
- [55] Aricak B, Cetin M, Erdem R, Sevik H, Cometen H. The usability of Scotch pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) as a biomonitor for traffic-originated heavy metal concentrations in Turkey. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*. 2020; 29(2), 1051-1057.
- [56] Ozel HB, Varol HN, Sevik H. The change of Mn concentration by organ and species in several edible plants. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*. 2021; 29(2), 474-480
- [57] Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozel HB, Ozel S, Cetin IZ. Changes in heavy metal accumulation in some edible landscape plants depending on traffic density. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2020; 192(2), 1-9.
- [58] Tózsér D, Magura T, & Simon E. Heavy metal uptake by plant parts of willow species: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. 2017; 336, 101-109.
- [59] Turkyilmaz A, Sevik H, & Cetin M. The use of perennial needles as bio-monitors for recently accumulated heavy metals. *Landscape Ecological Engineering*. 2018; 14(1), 115–120.
- [60] Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozel HB, & Pinar B. Determining toxic metal concentration changes in landscaping plants based on some factors. *Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health*. 2019; 12(8), 983-991.
- [61] Sevik H. The variation of chrome consantration in some landscape plants due to species, organ and traffic density. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*. 2021; 9(3), 595-600.
- [62] Hrivnák M, Paule L, Krajmerová D, Kulaç Ş, Şevik H, Turna İ, Tvauri I, Gömöry D. Genetic variation in Tertiary relics: The case of eastern-Mediterranean *Abies* (Pinaceae). *Ecology and Evolution*. 2017; 7(23), 10018-10030.
- [63] Imren E, Kurt R, Yucedag C, Bilir N, Ozel HB, Cetin M, Sevik H. Selection of superior clones by the multi-dimensional decision making techniques in scots pine seed orchard. *Journal of Forests*. 2021; 8(1), 13-22.
- [64] Koç. İ. Examination of gas exchange parameters of *Abies balsamea* (L.) Mill. and *Abies concolor* saplings, grown under various water regime, exposed to extreme drought stress at the end of the growing season. *Turkish Journal of Forest Science*. 2021; 5(2), 592-605.
- [65] Sevik H, Cetin M, Ozturk A, Yigit N, & Karakus O. Changes in micromorphological characters of *Platanus orientalis* L. leaves in Turkey. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*. 2019; 17(3), 5909-5921.
- [66] Koc I. Changes that may occur in temperature, rain, and climate types due to global climate change: the example of Düzce. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*. 2021; 9(8), 1545-1554.
- [67] Yildiz D, Nzokou P, Deligoz A, Koc I, Genc M. Chemical and physiological responses of four Turkish red pine (*Pinus brutia* Ten.) provenances to cold temperature treatments. *European Journal of Forest Research*. 2014; 133(5), 809-818.
- [68] Güney D, Bayraktar A, Atar F, Turna, İ. Effects of root undercutting, fertilization and thinning on seedling growth and quality of oriental beech (*Fagus orientalis* Lipsky) seedlings. *Artvin Çoruh Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi*. 2020; 21(2), 214-222.
- [69] Sevik H, Yahyaoglu Z, & Turna I. Determination of genetic variation between populations of *Abies nordmanniana* subsp. *bornmulleriana* Mattf according to some seed characteristics, genetic diversity in plants. Chapter. 2012; 12, 231-248.

- [70] Turkyilmaz A, Sevik H, Isinkaralar K, & Cetin M. Using *Acer platanoides* annual rings to monitor the amount of heavy metals accumulated in air. *Environmental Monitoring Assessment*. 2018; 190, 578.
- [71] Koç İ. The effect of global climate change on some climate parameters and climate types in Bolu. *Journal of Bartın Faculty of Forestry*. 2021; 23(2), 706-719.
- [72] Isinkaralar K. High-efficiency removal of benzene vapor using activated carbon from *Althaea officinalis* L. biomass as a lignocellulosic precursor. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2022; 29(44), 66728–66740.
- [73] Koç İ. Examining of seed germination rate and seedlings gas exchange performances of Anatolian black pine under water stress. *International Karabakh Applied Science Conference*. Khazar Univeristy, June 17-19, 2021. (Conference paper). 2021.
- [74] Sevik H, Isinkaralar K, & Isinkaralar O. Indoor air quality in hospitals: the case of Kastamonu Turkey. *Journal of Chemical, Biological, Physical Sciences, Sect D*. 2018; 9(1), 67-73.
- [75] Güney D, Yahyaoglu Z, Bayraktar A, Atar F, Turna I. Genetic diversity of *Picea orientalis* (L.) Link populations in Turkey. *Šumarski list*. 2019; 143(11-12), 539-547.
- [76] Yayla EE, Sevik H, & Isinkaralar K. Detection of landscape species as a low-cost biomonitoring study: Cr, Mn, and Zn pollution in an urban air quality. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*. 2022; 194(10), 1-10.
- [77] Cicek E, Tilki F, Kulac Ş, Yilmaz M, Yilmaz F. Survival and growth of three hardwood species (*Fraxinus angustifolia*, *Ulmus laevis* and *U. minor*) on a bottomland site with heavy clay soil. *Journal of Plant Sciences*. 2007; 2(2), 233-237.
- [78] Koc, I., & Nzokou, P. Effects of water stress and cold treatments on the germination of two conifers (*Pinus nigra* and *Pinus brutia*) species from Turkey. *Hortscience*. 2018; 53(9), 259-259.
- [79] Varol T, Cetin M, Ozel HB, Sevik H, Zeren Cetin I. The effects of climate change scenarios on *Carpinus betulus* and *Carpinus orientalis* in Europe. *Water, Air, Soil Pollution*. 2022; 233, 45.
- [80] Koç İ. Conifers response to water stress: physiological responses and effects on nutrient use physiology. [PhD. dissertation]. Michigan State University: 2019.
- [81] Sevik H, & Cetin M. Effects of some hormone applications on germination and morphological characters of endangered plant species *Lilium artvinense* L. onion scales. *Bulgarian Chemical Communications*. 2016; 48(2), 256-260.
- [82] Kravkaz-Kuscu IS, Sariyildiz T, Cetin M, Yigit N, Sevik H, & Savaci G. Evaluation of the soil properties and primary forest tree species in Taskopru (Kastamonu) district. *Fresenius Environmental Bulletin*. 2018; 27 (3), 1613-1617.
- [83] Shults P, Nzokou P, Koc I. Nitrogen contributions of alley cropped *Trifolium pratense* may sustain short rotation woody crop yields on marginal lands. *Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems*. 2020; 117(2), 261-272.
- [84] Koç, I. Comparison of the Gas Exchange Parameters of Two Maple Species (*Acer negundo* and *Acer pseudoplatanus*) Seedlings under Drought Stress. *Bartın Orman Fakültesi Dergisi*. 2022; 24(1), 65-76.
- [85] Özer Genç Ç, & Arıcağ B. Developing a harvest plan by considering the effects of skidding techniques on forest soil using a hybrid TOPSIS-Entropy Method. *Forest Science*. 2022; 68(3), 312-324.
- [86] Sulhan OF, Sevik H, & Isinkaralar K. Assessment of Cr and Zn deposition on *Picea pungens* Engelm. in urban air of Ankara, Türkiye. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*. 2022; 1-20.
- [87] Erdem R, Cetin M, Arıcağ B, & Sevik H. The Change of the Concentrations of B and Na in Some Forest Soils Depending on Plant Species. *Forestist*. 2023; (InPress).
- [88] Isinkaralar K, Koç İ, Kuzmina NA, Menshchikov SL, Erdem R, & Arıcağ B. Determination of heavy metal levels using *Betula pendula* Roth. under various soil contamination in Southern Urals, Russia. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*. 2022; 19(12), 12593-12604.
- [89] Isinkaralar K. Temporal variability of trace metal evidence in *Cupressus arizonica*, *Platanus orientalis*, and *Robinia pseudoacacia* as pollution-resistant species at an industrial site. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*. 2022; 233(7), 1-12.
- [90] Kuzmina N, Menshchikov S, Mohnachev P, Zavyalov K, Petrova I, Ozel HB, Arıcağ B, Onat SM, & Sevik H. Change of Aluminum Concentrations in Specific Plants by Species, Organ, Washing, and Traffic Density. *BioResources*. 2023; 18(1), 792-803.